

GH15A-06 - Assessing NASA's Open Source Science Outlook for Environmental Justice and Resilience of the Louisiana Gulf Coast (OSO-LoGiC)

Abstract

Environmental injustice persists, in part, when observations are unable to promote collective understanding and present patterns of harm in ways that decision makers cannot ignore. Individual complaints and marginalized voices too often lack accessible scientifically valid processes to aggregate evidence for sustainable and consequential action. Negative wellbeing outcomes for people and damage to the planet are frequently unmeasured and consequently go unaccounted for. Open Source Science broadens participation in the scientific process for more equitable policy response. Perhaps most importantly for resilience-oriented policy and policy implementation, Open Source Science inclusion of the private sector, public entities, academia and citizens builds common trust in the evidence that informs decisions and policy dialogues. The synoptic observational power of NASA data products to address domestic challenges remains largely underutilized even as it has played a decades long role in global monitoring of Earth system changes or informing resilience programing for agencies like USAID in planning international cooperation or emergency response. Increased temporal and spatial resolution of NASA data streams make previous research on global issues like climate change now tractable for decision support at more local levels. The resilience of the Louisiana Gulf Coast with a broad diversity of communities facing a wide-range of environmental challenges could potentially benefit the most as well as provide real world assessment of opportunities for value addition to NASA investments with greater inclusive and equitable engagement in Open Source Science. The OSO-LoGiC project assessed, with participatory engagement of the EJ organizations, to what extent Open Science can advance the impact of NASA investments to further equity, environmental justice, and resilience outcomes and their measurement in Louisiana. This work builds on Louisiana's comparative advantages as an established resilience science hub (environment, disaster, social, costal, and health sciences) and emergent 'Silicon Bayou' technology hub (data, decision support, and citizen science) to outline potential synergies of Open Source Science and Environmental Justice for improved resilience policy and policy implementation.